

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ
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АНДИЖОН МАШИНАСОЗЛИК ИНСТИТУТИ**

**«ТИЛШУНОСЛИК ВА РАҚАМЛИ ҲАЁТ: РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ
ВА МУАММОЛАР» МАВЗУСИДАГИ РЕСПУБЛИКА ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ
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**МАТЕРИАЛЫ РЕСПУБЛИКАНСКОЙ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЙ
КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ ПО ТЕМЕ «ЛИНГВИСТИКА И ЦИФРОВАЯ ЖИЗНЬ:
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HUMANIZING THE ROBOT IMAGE WITH THE HELP OF LANGUAGE MEANS IN “I, ROBOT” BY ISAAC ASIMOV

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Abstract. The article shows how language means were used by famous American science fiction writer Isaac Asimov to humanize the image of robot in his “I, Robot” story collection and, consequently, what was the purpose of that humanization. It is supposed that the image of robot in Asimov’s stories is half-metaphorical; it combines the traits of machines as well as human beings in order to reveal and investigate two approaches to reality – machinery and humane.

Keywords: image, robot, language means, Asimov, “I, Robot”, machine, human being, humanization.

Linguocultural characteristics of a literary image, known as “linguocultural type”, is an abstract mental formation considered as a kind of concept. The term “linguocultural type” seems to be the most suitable for the study and description of this kind of concepts, since it focuses, firstly, on the cultural and diagnostic significance of the typified image for understanding the corresponding culture, and, secondly, on the study of this image from the standpoint of linguistics” [1, 17].

The authors of science fiction create their works within the limits set by the level of contemporary science’s progress, and it is scientists who supply a significant part of the fantastic material. Within the science fiction discourse, we consider it legitimate to single out such a linguocultural type as a “robot”. In order to determine the conceptual component of the “robot” linguocultural type we consulted encyclopedia and found the following definition of the term “robot”: «a

machine that looks like a human being and performs various complex acts; a similar but fictional machine whose lack of capacity for human emotions is often emphasized; an efficient insensitive person who functions automatically; a mechanism guided by automatic controls” [2, 398]. It seems that the meanings of this word are ambivalent, reflecting the human perception of the robot.

Isaac Asimov is a founder of modern literature on robots and, in many respects, the creator of the modern image of “robot” as a linguocultural type. The writer managed to build a system according to which his followers created the series of robot characters. Analysis of stories from the “I, Robot” collection, in one way or another describing and revealing the essence of the robot, showed that the representation of the linguocultural type of the robot is based on the following figurative characteristics: externally humanlike, obedient to man, fast, quick-witted, unpredictable. In the creation of the “robot” type, an implicit characteristic prevails. One of the fundamental means of expressing implicitness is the use of religious allusions in the text, which have a rich semantic potential.

The title of the “I, Robot” collection, which sets the reader’s expectations, also carries a great semantic load. The title here is a phrase spoken in the first person and it declares that the characters of robots are individuals who can have their own consciousness, their own “I”.

The robot characters in Asimov’s stories are largely individualized. For Asimov, robots are not a single-faced mass – the writer gives each mechanical character his or her own characteristic features. It is achieved primarily through portrait characterization. In every story, the robot differs in its appearance: «They were large, extremely so, and even though they were in a sitting position on the floor, legs straddled out before them, their heads were a good seven feet in the air» [3, 32]. «His graceful, streamlined body threw out blazing highlights as he loped with easy speed across the broken ground» [3, 40]. By the appearance of the robot, a reader can guess his or her emotional reaction. For that reason, the

author often focuses on the appearance of his characters: «Herby’s eyes blinked white in astonishment» [3, 50]. The description of another robot is more poetic: «Robot QT-1 sat immovable. The burnished plates of his body gleamed and the glowing red of the photoelectric cells that were his eyes were fixed steadily upon the Earthman» [3, 67]. The description shows somewhat contemptuous attitude of the robot towards people, conveyed through words such as «immovable», «steadily», «Earthman».

All Asimov’s robots, regardless of the functions they perform, are created to resemble human beings; it reveals the inner “hidden” meaning of the robot image - metaphorical.

In addition, one of the means of creating the image of the character is speech characteristics. The speech characteristics of the robot image in Asimov’s stories are strongly humane, they do not use homogeneous and monotonous phrases. Their speech is literary, but it also contains colloquial elements such as interjections and elliptical sentences: «Hm-m-m!» [3, 32]. «But I don’t!» [3, 34]. «Of course not!» [3, 45].

The emotional coloring of the robot characters’ speech finds its confirmation in exclamation intonations, pauses, and breaks in remarks. In the story “Little Lost Robot” the robot seems to be confused, its thoughts get confused, two-part sentences prevail, separated by dashes instead of dots - a feeling of flow, fragmentary thoughts out loud is created: «I know a good deal – he would think – I mean I’ve been found – Disgraceful – Not I – I am intelligent – And am intelligent – And by a master ... who is weak – slow» [3,28].

In the story “Liar”, the robot’s words express despair, even hysteria: “Close your mind! It’s full of pain and frustration and hate! I didn’t mean it? I tell you! I tried to help!” [3, 81].

Asimov uses two types of language problems in his stories. The first type is a robot that understands everything literally, who is given an order in a figurative

sense. The second is a robot that has received an order in which a word is used that has a different meaning for a robot than for a person. In the story “Little Lost Robot”, an annoyed engineer orders the overly helpful robot “Go lose yourself!”, and robot follows the order, taking the command given to him to literally. “Go lose yourself” does not mean “go hide”, but “go away”. Asimov’s robots perceive English and speak it, not understanding all its idiomaticity. In the story “Risk”, a robot is told to pull the control bar firmly (“Pull the control bar back firmly”). But the adverb “firmly” for a robot means applying much more force than for a human - the robot bends the lever and fails the experiment.

The way robots speak and the sound characteristics of their voices are of great importance. Each of them has its own characteristics: «Then, in a harsh, squawking voice, like that of a medieval phonograph, he greeted, ‘Yes, Master!’» [3, 32]. «Herby subsided silently, and muttered in a low voice from which the metallic timbre disappeared almost entirely» [3, 71]. «He was equipped with an excellent diaphragm, and the presence of overtones in the sound unit robbed him of much of that metallic flatness that mark the usual robot voice» [3, 91].

In describing the sound of the robot’s voice, stylistically colored vocabulary is used («overtones», «to mutter», «to murmur», «to rob of something», «the metallic timbre», «the metallic flatness»); such kind of vocabulary also humanizes the image of the robot.

Thus, in the speech portrait of the robot image in Asimov’s stories, its ambiguity and unpredictability are manifested.

An important role in the creation of variants of the artistic image of the robot is played by the attitude of the character that connects all the stories of the collection "I, Robot" - robotics specialist Susan Calvin. Its assessment helps the author to characterize the robots. In communicating with robots, Susan shows more human qualities than in communicating with people, since she is engaged in the psychology of robots, and she is extremely interested in them. Robots, unlike

humans, cannot hurt a person, and this makes Susan sympathetic and friendly towards them: «Please, don't get excited, boy. I'm not blaming you for anything» [3, 58]. When Susan talks about robots, her words show excitement, heightened emotionality, which is expressed with the help of stylistic means and emotionally colored vocabulary: «To you, a robot is a robot. Gears and metal, electricity and positrons, mind and iron! Human-made! If necessary, human can destroy it! They are a cleaner better bread than we are...» [3, 70]. «There was a time when humanity faced the universe alone and without a friend. Now he has creatures to help him, stronger creatures than himself, more faithful, more useful, and absolutely devoted to him» [3, 36]. It is also expressed in the words of a journalist talking to Susan: «Susan Calvin talked about Powell and Donovan with unsmiling amusement, but warmth came into her voice when she mentioned robots» [3, 39]. It is no coincidence that in the story “Liar” Susan has friendly feelings for one of her colleagues, she shares her feelings with one of the robots. During this conversation, her speech changes, becoming more abrupt and emotional, less clear. In the text, this is conveyed through breaks in remarks, pauses, defaults, paragraphemics: «Have you – told anyone?» [3, 40]. «But I am so ... so ...» [3, 42]. «I want to ... to congratulate you, of course. I'm very glad...» [3, 49].

To summarize, an analysis of literary texts, in which the investigated type is actualized, showed that Asimov's robots are very close to people. For Asimov, the robot image created by him is both a means and a goal. The writer feels fear about the descent of a person to the level of a robot, his loss of the gift of compassion, feelings of love, friendship. Asimov's robot is conditional, it is a kind of intermediate link between a mechanical being and a person, it serves to emphasize the imperfection of a person, push him towards self-development, self-education.

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